

TITLE RENAL FAILURE AFTER CARDIOPULMONARY BYPASS: INSUFFICIENT REMOVAL OF MIDDLE MOLECULES BY PERITONEAL DIALYSIS

AUTHORS Russo L., Narducci C., Natili F., Carnabuci A., D'Alessandro L.C.

ADDRESS Divisione di Cardiochirurgia, O. San Camillo, Roma, Huggins Laboratory, Colli di Cicerone, Genzano, Roma, Servizio di Emodialisi, O. San Camillo, Roma

Patients who undergo cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB) for open heart surgery have increased amounts of middle molecules in plasma in post-operative period. When acute renal failure supervenes the prognosis is particularly severe for the concomitant post-perfusional damage. We have studied free and weakly bound middle molecules after CPB in plasma of 11 patients with normal renal function and 6 patients with renal failure treated with peritoneal dialysis, by ultrafiltration or anafiltration and gel chromatography on Sephadex G-25. All patients showed the typical increase of the peptidic peak at the end of the extra corporeal circulation. Patients with renal failure presented the appearance of middle molecular peak. They were treated with peritoneal dialysis and no modification of anafiltrated peaks was observed even after 4 days of therapy. Middle molecules were determined also in peritoneal liquid and the ratio middle:small molecules peak determined in filtered plasma and in dialysis fluid. Results have shown a mean ratio 1:3 in plasma versus 1:7 in liquid. The hypothesis of the presence of toxic bound middle molecules in patients with renal failure after CPB, due to associated liver damage, and resistant to the usual procedures is discussed.